

REVERTER

Policy Recommendations: Tackling Energy Poverty in Vulnerable Households via Deep Renovations

This brief provides targeted policy recommendations for four pilot regions - **Brezovo (Bulgaria)**, **Coimbra (Portugal)**, **Athens (Greece)**, and **Riga (Latvia)** - as well as for the EU level, outlining the key barriers, solutions, and priority actions to scale up deep renovations for vulnerable households, based on findings of the REVERTER project.

EU Level

A delivery framework for vulnerable-first deep renovation

Goal: Create a coherent EU framework that standardises identification, enables predictable financing, professionalises OSS & ambassadors, and embeds health and inclusion in renovation programmes.

Core Actions:

- Require interoperable national observatories using admin/survey data, privacy-by-design, and open tools.
- Require annual aligned HBS and EU SILC and fund pilot statistical models to pre-qualify households/buildings for support ('auto-eligibility' letters).
- Integrate energy poverty into social/climate budgeting; require 100% subsidy options for the most vulnerable with pre-application cost coverage.
- Blend EU funds with national/private sources.
- Promote multi-annual envelopes, municipal aggregation, and guarantee facilities for condo projects
- Co-fund national/regional OSS and training hubs; standardise energy ambassadors training; support paid outreach roles with peer-learning networks.
- Establish EU commissioning/QA protocols, certifications, post-works monitoring with public dashboards, and cost-stabilisation mechanisms.
- Prioritise inclusion and engagement with multilingual campaigns, pre-visit checklists, and social-service partnerships; embed health outcomes (mould/humidity-related) as core indicators.

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Brezovo (Bulgaria)

Trust-first delivery and inclusive financing in small municipalities

Goal: Enable high-quality deep renovations for vulnerable households through trusted local outreach, while supporting regional One-Stop Shops (OSS) with targeted policies and ensuring inclusive, predictable financing, especially for small, under-resourced municipalities.

Key Barriers: Lack of a national information system to identify and monitor EP; lack of local data; insufficient municipal human/technical resources; weak OSS policy framework; lack of financial instruments for single-family house renovations; heavy reliance on inefficient heating systems.

Priority Actions:

- Develop a national information system for identifying energy poverty.
- Enable data sharing between municipalities, energy and social services, and OSS.
- Strengthen and scale OSSs; incentivise private sector participation.
- Support municipalities in planning renovation goals and community engagement.
- Design inclusive financing instruments; ensure budget for OSS staff.
- Develop tailored financial tools for households in small municipalities with simplified access.
- Offer micro-grants for quick-win measures (e.g. windows, basic insulation, new heating).
- Provide zero-interest loans with guarantees for deeper renovations, targeting low- and middle-income homeowners.

Athens (Greece)

Finance without fear: cut bureaucracy, cover upfronts, provide professionalised support

Goal: Raise completion of deep renovations among vulnerable groups by de-risking finance, simplifying processes, and scaling personalised support via OSS and Energy Ambassadors.

Key Barriers: Overstretched volunteer OSS, high upfront costs, restrictive eligibility, ownership issues (e.g. households unable to pay the inheritance tax, they cannot apply for a subsidy, as they are not the legal owners), and behavioural biases.

Priority Actions:

- Cover pre-application costs (energy performance certificate-EPC, consultancy) regardless of outcome.
- Offer 100% subsidies for vulnerable households; offer no-debt options; longer windows; simple, stable rules; plain-language guidance; simplify applications.
- Incentivise multi-apartment renovations; aggregate projects for scale.
- Hire and stabilise professional OSS staff with tiered ambassador/expert models; integrate social workers for complex cases.
- Run campaigns linking renovations to health and mental well-being.

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Riga (Latvia)

Unlock condominium decision making and make funding predictable

Goal: Raise renovation decision making and delivery in Soviet-era multi-apartment buildings by removing decision making bottlenecks, stabilising funds, and focusing outreach on useful information over strict surveys.

Key Barriers: Data and automated targeting gaps, unstable funding horizons, staff shortages, weak condominium decision laws, and low household interest.

Priority Actions:

- Define energy poverty and build automated data systems.
- Introduce minority or qualified-majority voting for deep renovation decisions and financing; provide mediation for conflict resolution.
- Secure multi-annual funding envelopes for worst-performing buildings; include municipal co-financing for low-income units.
- Run campaigns on benefits and stability of expenses; guarantee lines and performance-based grants to de-risk projects; provide continuous education.

Coimbra (Portugal)

Social housing: pair deep retrofits with tenant co-responsibility

Goal: Shift from fragmented fixes to staged deep renovation of municipal stock, while building tenant co-responsibility and ensuring proper commissioning and user education.

Key Barriers: The municipality (owner of the social housing) faced financial constraints for a long time. As a result, renovations did not improve energy performance. Fragmented policies, a lack of skilled labour and limited interest from contractors also hampered progress.

Priority Actions:

- Ensure sustainable financing: channel European/national funds to municipalities; explore energy performance contracts and public-private partnerships for complementary investments.
- Establish stricter regulations: define minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) for social housing and introduce quality requirements in public tenders to ensure effective renovations.
- Strengthen resident participation: involve tenants in planning, decision-making and post-renovation training to ensure acceptance and correct use of the new systems.
- Improve coordination: align energy, social, and housing policies.
- Promote social and economic benefits: link deep renovations to job creation, improved health, and lower household energy bills, reinforcing the perception of renovations as a social right and an economic opportunity.
- Strengthen OSS with external facilitators and digital platforms; use a neutral OSS brand to reduce tension between landlords and tenants; provide on-site advice.

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Deep REnovation roadmaps to decrease households VulnERability To Energy poveRty

The main objective of the REVERTER project

By providing citizens with comprehensive information and realistic building renovation solutions, the REVERTER consortium aims to reduce energy poverty in Europe.

REVERTER

The REVERTER project team has worked collaboratively to conduct surveys, create nine deep renovation roadmaps, develop a comprehensive methodology for One-Stop Shops (OSS), create training materials, and ensure their effective delivery. In addition, the team has successfully supported the establishment of OSS across various regions, helping to promote energy efficiency and alleviate energy poverty.

Building on the knowledge and experience gained throughout the project, the consortium has also developed a set of policy recommendations aimed at guiding future actions and strengthening support frameworks for energy-efficient home renovations and energy poverty reduction across Europe.

Project results

- Replication
- REVERTERup!
- Roadmaps
- REVERTER Atlas
- Deliverables
- Energy saving tips
- One-Stop-Shops
- Training materials

You can find all
project results
and documents
on project
website!

Find our project
results on
Zenodo!

*From energy poverty to energy dignity: creating safe, affordable,
and efficient homes for vulnerable households*

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